

groundbreaking research...

educational affiliations...

conferences
& other publicity...

New Zealand
Microbiological
Society

national recognition...

 The Royal Society of New Zealand
promoting excellence in science and technology

who & what we are

Introduction

Established 1997

Encompasses Arts, Journalism, Commerce, Sports Science and Technology

Providing an outlet for suppressed students creativity and excellence

Published Two NZMS 1999, NZMS 2001, NZASE CDROM, SciCon 2000

History

Space to work in

Expansion opportunities

who & what we are

Who

Accepting members from the whole nation

Open to every age, ethnicity and ability

Current age range is 8-18

What

Promotes life skills such as

Time Management

Self-Esteem

Critical Thinking

Initiative

Opens opportunities for

Leadership

Self Direction

Develops students on strengths, rather than highlighting weakness

who & what we are

Why

Increases motivation

Develops Professionalism

Provides constructive, fun, channel for students efforts

making a positive change in the world around us...

what we have done, are doing and will do

Expertise

Our age, experience and education make people think

We won't meet our goals

We are set up to fail

It's not what you know, but who you know

what we have done, are doing and will do

Expertise

We are also associated with and receive advice from:

Alan Cooper

World expert in ancient DNA recovery

Mark Tredwill

Started a small physics group in 1990 in Tokoroa

Royal Society of New Zealand

This prestigious society is presenting our work to the ministry of education

Microbiology Society of New Zealand

Assisted with conferences in 1999/2001, offer advice and guidance

Western Institute of Technology in Taranaki

Fully equipped research lab (but we still have no meeting place or computer labs)

what we have done, are doing and will do

Expertise

Five years running experience

Senior members pass knowledge and experience on

What we have done

We are succeeding

Achievements recognized by

Secondary and tertiary institutions

National societies

International research laboratories

what we have done, are doing and will do

Achievements

1999 & 2001 Conferences

Highlighted developments in health, medicine, agriculture, biotechnology
NRG students the youngest presenters ever

Microbiology Misconceptions In Secondary Schools

One of our many research papers, articles, addresses and seminars
Discusses health hazards from incorrect school practices
Presented to the Ministry Of Education

Caulobacter Species

New Zealands leading research laboratory
One of the few in the world studying the bacterium
Transfer anti-biotic resistance to other medically important organisms
Research can prevent illness

what we have done, are doing and will do

Achievements

Resources

DNA isolation and electrophoresis protocols

Our extensive and informative website has received a number of awards

Doing

Supplying schools with microbiology cultures

Alternative education paths

Early School Certificate

Polytechnic to replace two years schooling

Student Committee

Allows for student input

Law, politics, ethics, public relations, safety, environment and economics

what we have done, are doing and will do

Will do

Summer School

- Computer technology
- Space Research
- Electronics
- Business development
- Team Management skills
- Image engineering
- Aviation
- Amateur radio
- Languages
- Performing arts
- Journalism

Economical growth

WITT partnership, holiday destination, jobs and education

giving back to the community

What and why we provide

Education officially inadequate

In Funding, Expertise and Time

Nexus offers extension for students

Through knowledge and practical skills

Microbiology, to mathematics and even the arts

Providing for local community

Radio Station

Computers working on curing cancer

Sport injury research

Taranaki, New Zealand or even the world...

giving back to the community

Skills and opportunities

Promotes

- Productivity
- Enthusiasm
- Vibrancy
- Determination
- Good work habits
- Life Skills
- Time management

Summer School

- Benefits Public
- Will educate about the fascinating world we live in

you need us, we need you

Summary

Why should professional people come to Taranaki when the main centres have more educational opportunities for their children?

We believe the Council should have a policy for assisting with and nurturing new educational initiatives such as the NRG.

The NRG has a proven track record of achieving excellence and educational "firsts" - all on a voluntary basis.

The NRG is unique in New Zealand and ahead of its time - that is why professional people should come here!

you need us, we need you

Assistance

A home base - rooms for meetings, non-science projects and storage

Equipment (furniture, data projector, laptops)

Salary for full or half time position to make Taranaki a truly "NRG" province

Advice on business development, patent searches and funding of the costs involved

Advice on seeking sponsorship/partnerships with businesses or individuals

Sponsorship to travel to attend and present research at this years NZMS conference in Auckland

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New Plymouth District Council

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